

The Constancy of the Ratio of Carbon to Nitrogen in Natural Systems Undergoing Oxidation and the Problem of Protein Synthesis.

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In publications (Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry"; 1932; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 699; 1934, 11, 145) from these laboratories, it has been emphasised that the phenomenon of oxidation is only of importance to animal life but is of great importance to plant and soil processes and the laws governing all these oxidations appear to be identical.

The phenomenon of oxidation taking place in nature has been found to be markedly accelerated by sunlight, increase of temperature of the reacting systems and the presence of inductors (iron compound) and surfaces acting as catalytic agents.

In tropical countries, where there is plenty of sunshine, the influence of light and increased temperature due to the absorption of solar energy, play important rôle in animal, plant and soil oxidation reactions.

In this communication it will be shown that the constancy of C:N ratio exists not only in the soil but is also observed in animal metabolism as well. It seems that when a mixture of organic compounds containing nitrogenous substances present in natural systems undergoes oxidation in air, a constant ratio of C:N is finally attained.

Constancy of C:N ratio in the Products of Oxidation in Soil and in the Animal Body.

Analysis of different soils with various amounts of organic matter shows a nearly constant ratio between the elements carbon and nitrogen. This ratio which has the value 10 varies within narrow limits in normal soils. It is well known that in soil, which is well aerated, the chemical changes affecting carbon and nitrogen present in the soil are intimately connected. The combined nitrogen existing in soil can form nitrate only if the ratio of C to N is smaller than 10. When the proportion of carbon is greater, the excess is oxidised to CO₂ and the nitrogen remains as protein. When on the other-hand, the proportion of nitrogen becomes greater than the above ratio, the nitrogenous compound is converted into ammonia and nitrate, which may be absorbed by the plant or lost from the soil through different agencies. The observations of Leighty and Shorey

(*Soil Science*, 1930, 30, 257) that in the majority of soils examined by them, C:N ratio varied from 7 to 15 and in extreme cases the ratio could be as small as 3 and as large as 35. It seems to the author that the soils examined by these workers were not properly aerated for a sufficiently long time. The following results obtained by Lyon, Bizzell and Wilson (*J. Amer. Chem. Agron.*, 1923, 15, 457) show that no available nitrogen is added to the soil when a large amount of cellulose or other carbonaceous compound is present with the nitrogenous material added as fertilisers.

TABLE I.

Nitrate content of soil to which roots were added and left to decompose for 3 months.

Material used.	Nitrogen.	Wt. of roots added.	Nitrate nitrogen in leachings.
Control soil	946.6 mg.
Oat roots	0.45%	133.3 g.	207.3
Timothy roots	0.62	96.8	398.4
Maize roots	0.79	75.9	510.6
Clover roots	1.71	35.1	924.4
Dried blood	10.71	5.6	1751.1

It will be evident from the following experiments of Sievers and Holtz (*Washington State Coll. Agric. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1926, 43, 206) that not only the ratio of carbon to nitrogen existing in soil is constant but the ratio of carbon to nitrogen oxidised from the organic substances present in soil is also nearly constant and has the value not far from 10.

TABLE II.

Decomposition of soil organic matter for 142 days.

Nitrogen in soil.	Carbon in soil.	C : N ratio in soil.	CO ₂ liberated (as carbon).	Nitrate nitrogen formed, parts per million.	C : N ratio of the oxidation products.
0.091%	0.910%	10.0	119.6 mg.	15.4	7.8
0.143	1.684	11.8	187.6	18.3	10.2
0.155	1.860	12.0	167.5	17.6	9.5
0.233	2.889	12.4	230.9	26.3	8.8

The constancy of C:N in the soil processes has been ascribed to the activities of micro organisms but it will be evident from the following considerations that the constancy of C:N may be maintained even in the absence of bacteria in many natural systems undergoing oxidation.

It has been observed that in the presence of sodium arsenite, which does not oxidise when exposed to air but becomes oxidised to sodium arsenate when added to sodium sulphite, which is readily oxidised in air, the velocity of the oxidation of sodium sulphite by air is markedly retarded. Similarly, the presence of carbohydrates, which are themselves oxidised when mixed with sodium sulphite, ferrous hydroxide or cerous hydroxide or any other suitable reducing agent, markedly diminishes the velocity of the oxidation of the last named substances. We have arrived at the generalisation that in oxidation reactions, the phenomenon of negative catalysis is observed when the catalyst is a reducing agent.

Moreover, carbohydrates, fats and proteins have been oxidised by simply passing air through solutions or suspensions of these substances in presence of sunlight. Palit and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 1263; 1930, 34, 711, 993) have carried out experiments on the induced and photochemical oxidations of mixtures of carbohydrates, fats and proteins with each other and have arrived at the interesting conclusion that the presence of any one of these substances, which is itself undergoing oxidation, retards the oxidation of others.

In normal health, the heat and energy of the body are supplied to the system from the simultaneous combustion of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. The results obtained in these laboratories conclusively prove that the oxidation of fat is retarded by carbohydrates and perhaps less powerfully by proteins. Physiologists have reported that if all the carbohydrates in the food is replaced by fat, the fat is incompletely oxidised. In other words, for the complete combustion of fat in the body, carbohydrate must burn. V. Plimmer and R. H. A. Plimmer ("Vitamins and the Choice of Food," 1922, p. 5) have stated the position in the following words:—"Mixed with carbohydrate, it is as if fats burn with a clear flame but if there is too little carbohydrate, it burns smokily. The half burnt products of fat are poisonous to the body and produce coma." Similar results have been obtained by Chakravarti and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 617) *in vitro* and it has been observed that the velocity

of the oxidation of fats and fatty acids is decreased by the presence of carbohydrates and the amount of acetone bodies obtained by the oxidation of fats and fatty acids by H_2O_2 and iron salts decrease considerably when carbohydrates are added to the fats. Hence for the complete oxidation of fats, their velocity of oxidation must be decreased by carbohydrates *in vitro* and *in vivo*. It seems fairly certain now that the presence of either one or two of the above substances, which are undergoing oxidation, retards the oxidation of the third. It is, therefore, evident that in the presence of a large excess of carbohydrate or fat, little protein is burnt. The protein-sparing qualities of carbohydrates and fats were discovered from feeding experiments by some of the earliest students of metabolism and it is believed that carbohydrates are the more efficient of the two in sparing proteins. It has also been proved by Lusk, Landegren and others (compare Lusk, "Science of Nutrition", 1919, p. 269) that the withdrawal of carbohydrates from the food increases the protein metabolism. Moreover, in diabetes, where the glucose passes out unoxidised, there is considerable waste of tissue protein.

It will be interesting to note that in starvation, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen metabolism (oxidation) is not far from 10 to 1 as will be evident from the following table.

TABLE III.

Animal	Dog	Fowl	Guineapig	Rabbit
Ratio of C and N oxidised in starvation				9.5	10.8	7.6	9.7

The above results have been calculated from the observations recorded in Lusk's "Science of Nutrition", 1919, p. 86.

If the starvation is continued further, the value of C:N becomes less than 10, as will be seen in the following results obtained with a dog kept on long starvation.

TABLE IV.

Days of starvation	4th-13th	14th-15th	16th-23rd	24th-30th	31st-35th	36th	37th	38th
Ratio of C and N oxidation starvation	10.3	9.3	9.01	8.6	8.0	6.0	5.8	5.5

These results have been calculated from the observations of Voit (*Z. Biol.*, 1901, 41, 545). In other words, in long-continued starvation leading to death, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen undergoing oxidation, nearly attains the value 6, which is nearly the ratio

of carbon to nitrogen present in the animal body. It appears that in animal metabolism, the oxidation of carbonaceous substances (fats and carbohydrates) and proteins is guided by more or less the same relations as obtained in the soil and both these oxidation processes appear to be similar in nature.

In the soil, the oxidation of carbonaceous matter and proteins seems to be similarly controlled. The carbonaceous substances, such as cellulose, lignin, pentosan, glucose, etc., added to the soil retard the oxidation of the amino acids obtained from protein decomposition and hence in presence of large amounts of straw, hay, etc., very little amino acid oxidation to ammonia by air is possible and thus the nitrogen in the protein, present in the soil, remains unavoidable for the plants. Just as the process of ammonification in soil is retarded by carbonaceous matter, similarly the process of nitrification is also slowed down by carbonaceous matter, because both ammonification and nitrification are mainly oxidation reactions.

In the following tables obtained from the results of Lipman and associates [*N.J. Agr. Exp. Sta. Bull.*, 1912, 247] the retarding influence of carbohydrates on ammonification is well brought out.

TABLE V.

Organic substance 4 g.	Total nitrogen in substance.	Ammonia formed in milligrams.			
		No carbo- hydrate.	Glucose 2 g.	Sucrose 2 g.	Starch 2 g.
Wheat flour	94.8	5.14	3.66	5.84	1.56
Cowpea meal	156.8	50.88	31.71	28.57	23.70
Linseed meal	247.0	110.69	96.01	60.73	63.34
Soybean meal	245.6	129.64	108.03	94.88	54.36
Cotton seed meal	246.1	123.63	99.67	97.23	54.54
Corn meal	51.2	1.18	1.30	1.04	0.69

TABLE VI.

Influence of sugar on ammonia formation from 2% peptone solution.

Incubation period.	Sugar added.	NH ₃ -N in 100 c.c.
5 days	0%	44.80 mg.
5	1	40.74
5	2	14.14
5	5	1.26
5	20	0
15	0	73.08
15	1	50.68
15	2	36.54
15	5	33.04
15	20	0

Similarly the addition of glucose to casein causes a decrease in the amount of casein decomposed and ammonia formed. The same behaviour is also observed with glucose and dried blood.

The results of Hill (*Virginia Agric. Exp. Station Tech. Bull.*, 1915, 6) recorded in the following table show that the addition of carbonaceous matter to soil leads to the decrease in nitrate formation.

TABLE VII.

Nitric nitrogen in milligrams in 100 grams dry soil.

Organic matter added (0.3-0.6 per cent.).	At the beginning.	After, weeks					
		12	20	24	28	32	40
None	0.59	0.74	0.55	1.25	1.50	3.51	2.65
Paper	0.59	0	0	trace	trace	0.20	1.29

The addition of one per cent dextrose to soil markedly retards the formation of nitrate in soil.

It is generally believed that the nitrite and nitrate forming bacteria can live mainly on the energy obtained from the oxidations of ammonium salt to nitrite and nitrite to nitrate and glucose, peptone, gelatine, asparagine and other organic substances are harmful. This follows from the view point advanced in this paper. The organic substances act as retarding agents in the oxidation of ammonium salts to nitrite and of nitrite to nitrate and hence the energy supply to the bacteria is cut off and their growth checked by the presence of organic substances, which act as negative catalysts in the oxidation processes.

From the foregoing considerations, it is clear that the carbonaceous matter present in soil acts as an agent in sparing the soil protein from oxidation, just as carbohydrates preserve the body protein from undergoing oxidation. The retarding influence of carbohydrates and other carbonaceous compounds on the rate of oxidation of proteins to ammonia and of ammonium salts to nitrite has been observed with different types of micro-organisms having different protein and energy requirements. Moreover, this retarding influence is not restricted to oxidations due to micro-organisms. Investigations carried on in the author's laboratories show that this phenomenon of the decrease of the velocity of oxidation is of general occurrence and is observed with catalytic, induced and photochemical oxidation reactions involving a mixture of organic compounds containing nitrogenous substances. (Compare Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry," 1932, p. 44; Palit

and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 711). The current explanation of the retarding influence of carbonaceous compounds on protein oxidation and the constancy of C:N ratio in soils, based on the energy requirements of the micro-organisms first emphasised by Doryland (*N. Dakota Agric. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1916, 116) has to be revised in view of the fact that the retarding effect appears to be a general phenomenon occurring in chemical, catalytic, physiological, soil and photochemical oxidation processes in which a mixture of organic compounds is undergoing oxidation. Moreover, there is considerable loss of energy in the process of deamination of proteins and hence the energy requirements of the micro-organisms may not be the controlling factor in regulating the amounts of proteins and carbohydrates oxidised in soil processes.

Ratio of C:N and Protein Synthesis.

Recently the authors (Dhar and Mukherji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 727) have shown that amino acids are readily formed *in vitro* by the reaction of solutions of nitrates and carbohydrates or substances which produce carbohydrates when exposed to sunlight in presence of titania and no amino acid is synthesised in the dark or by the reaction of ammonium salts and carbohydrates even in light. Moreover, we have been able to produce evidence showing the formation of arginine *in vitro* by exposing solutions of glucose and potassium nitrate to sunlight in presence of titania. It is well known that the percentage of arginine is largest amongst the amino acids obtained from plant proteins. It seems, therefore, that the amino acids in plants are synthesised from carbohydrates and nitrates and that sunlight is an important agency in this reaction and the plant pigments are likely to behave as photo-sensitisers, just as titania acts as a sensitiser in the photosynthesis of amino acids *in vitro*.

Moreover, it will be evident from Table II that the nitrate concentration of the soil decreases when carbonaceous matters like oat roots, timothy roots, maize roots etc., are added. Apart from the formation of proteins by the action of the micro-organisms on the nitrates and carbonaceous substances, it is possible that amino acids are also photosynthesised by the reaction of nitrates and carbonaceous compounds in presence of light. This photosynthesis of amino acids may be responsible for the decrease of nitrate concentration in soil when carbonaceous compounds are added.

It has been stated that the rice plant takes up ammonium salts in the beginning of its development and nitrate in the end. Moreover plants like barley, maize, and pumpkins, which are rich in carbohydrates, readily absorb ammonium salts. It seems that in these plants, in the beginning, the plants contain a very large amount of carbohydrate and little protein and thus the C:N ratio may be much greater than 10:1 and hence the ammonia is absorbed; whilst in the end the protein accumulation takes place due to the energy supplied by the oxidation of carbohydrates and thus the ratio of C:N has a tendency to have the value 10:1 and that is why ammonium salts are not required. Hence it seems that where the C:N ratio is much greater than 10:1, ammonium salts may be absorbed. However, the legumes and beans should at no stage grow with ammonium salts. On the other hand, starch producing plants at certain stages when the carbohydrate content is high and protein content low, may be fed and made to grow well by ammonium salts. It is believed that the ease of ammonia absorption depends on the velocity with which it is converted into asparagine and this in turn depends on the amount of carbohydrates, which are also necessary for protein synthesis.

CONCLUSION.

The following conclusions have been arrived at from a comprehensive estimate of the results of the author and other workers.

1. Not only the ratio of carbon to nitrogen in the compound existing in soil is constant but the ratio of carbon to nitrogen in the products of oxidation of organic compounds in soil is also nearly constant and is approximately 10.

2. In starvation, the ratio of carbon to nitrogen oxidised in the metabolism of different animals is also not far from 10. It seems that when a mixture of organic compounds undergoes oxidation in air the ratio of carbon to nitrogen oxidised is nearly 10 and this appears to be a general phenomenon.

3. Just as carbohydrates preserve the body protein from undergoing oxidation, the carbonaceous matter present in the soil protects the soil protein from oxidation. The retarding influence of carbohydrates and other carbonaceous compounds on the oxidation of proteins to ammonia and ammonium salts to nitrite has been observed with different micro-organisms having varied protein and

energy requirements and hence it is assumed that the energy requirements of the micro-organisms may not be the controlling factor in regulating the amounts of proteins and carbohydrates oxidised in soil processes.

4. The protein-sparing qualities of carbohydrates arise from the fact that carbohydrates decrease the oxidation of proteins when both these groups of substances undergo oxidation and this behaviour forms a part of the generalisation that the phenomenon of negative catalysis (retardation) is observed in an oxidation reaction, when the catalyst is a reducing agent.

5. Amino acids are readily synthesised *in vitro* when a solution of a nitrate and carbohydrates is exposed to sunlight in presence of titania. It seems likely that the energy obtained from the oxidation of carbohydrates by nitrates or oxygen is necessary for protein synthesis in plants. The assimilation of ammonium salts by plants in protein synthesis is possible when the carbohydrate content is high and depends on the C:N ratio.

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